

ADAPTIVE SUPERRESOLUTION USING THE RECURSIVE SUPPRESSION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

The Recursive Suppression Algorithm for adaptive super-resolution is analyzed. Simulation results verify the effectiveness of this algorithm in resolving closely spaced signals and show that it achieves resolution approximately as rapidly as the computationally intensive MUSIC algorithm. The concept of resolution stability and the choice of the adaptation constant are explained.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive superresolution algorithms are potentially much simpler to implement than the computationally intensive covariance-based or model-based algorithms, which have received by far the most attention in the literature. Adaptive algorithms that entail batch estimation of eigenvectors can match the performance of covariance-based algorithms and are more capable of tracking the bearing of a source when either the source or the array is mobile [1]. The simplest of the superresolution algorithms estimate a single eigenvector corresponding to the smallest eigenvalue of the covariance matrix but do not provide performance as good as that of other superresolution algorithms [2]. The Recursive Suppression algorithm is only slightly more computationally complex but offers a faster convergence and a more accurate bearing estimate than the other algorithms that estimate a single eigenvector. As discussed subsequently, the Recursive Suppression algorithm appears to offer performance comparable to that of the MUSIC algorithm [3] while requiring far less computation.

A simple adaptive superresolution system can be decomposed into two parts, as illustrated in Figure 1. The antenna outputs are applied to an adaptive filter that uses one of the adaptive algorithms to automatically adjust its weights so that the array pattern, which is the pattern associated with the antenna elements plus the adaptive filter, has small gains in the directions of received signals. The weight values are applied to a weight processor, which computes the array pattern. The pattern is examined to determine at what angles the pattern exhibits local minima and falls below some specified threshold. These angles provide the estimated bearings of the received signals.

The primary application of the Recursive Suppression algorithm is to support the adaptive superresolution system of Figure 1. However, the algorithm can be used independently to suppress interference whenever the desired signal is absent or appears with low probability as an input to the algorithm. The latter situation occurs during signal acquisition in an adaptive antenna system for frequency-hopping communications [4].

II. RECURSIVE SUPPRESSION ALGORITHM

The Recursive Suppression algorithm can be derived by the method of steepest descent with the constrained minimization of the output power of an adaptive filter as the performance criterion. In the derivation, we assume that the desired signal and the interference can be modeled as stationary stochastic processes. Let $\mathbf{W}$ denote the complex weight vector and $\mathbf{X}(t)$ denote the vector of the received signal at the adaptive-filter input. The components of $\mathbf{X}(t)$ are analytic signals. Let an asterisk denote the complex conjugate, T the transpose, and H the conjugate transpose. The analytic signal at the system output is

$$y_d(t) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{X}(t) = \mathbf{X}^T(t) \mathbf{W} \quad (1)$$

The mean output power is

$$P_x = \frac{1}{2} E [|y_d(t)|^2] \quad (2)$$

In terms of its real part $\mathbf{W}_R$ and its imaginary part $\mathbf{W}_I$, a complex weight vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_R - j\mathbf{W}_I, \quad (3)$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$.

Since the adaptive filter in the adaptive superresolution system is intended to produce nulls in the directions to all signal sources, a plausible performance criterion is the constrained minimum-power criterion. The constraint is placed upon the norm of the weight vector so that the optimal weight vector is not the zero vector. Thus, the

Figure 1. Adaptive superresolution system.

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performance criterion requires the minimization of the mean output power P_x subject to the quadratic constraint

$$\|\mathbf{W}\|^2 = \mathbf{W}^H \mathbf{W} = \beta^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\|\mathbf{W}\|$ denotes the norm of $\mathbf{W}$ and β is a scalar constant.

Let $\mathbf{W}(k)$ denote the complex weight vector after iteration k of the adaptive algorithm. The analytic output signal between iterations is

$$y_d(t) = \mathbf{X}^T(t) \mathbf{W}(k), \quad t_k \leq t < t_{k+1} \quad (5)$$

where t_k is the time of iteration k .

Using Lagrange multipliers and the method of steepest descent, we obtain the Recursive Suppression algorithm [5]. The algorithm is

$$\mathbf{W}(k+1) = \frac{\beta \mathbf{V}(k+1)}{\|\mathbf{V}(k+1)\|} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{V}(k+1) = \mathbf{W}(k) - \mu \mathbf{Z}(k\gamma + \gamma) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}(i+1) = \alpha(i) \mathbf{Z}(i) + \frac{1-\alpha(i)}{T_0} \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} \mathbf{X}^*(t) y_d(t) dt, \quad (8)$$

$$k\gamma + 1 \leq i \leq (k+1)\gamma - 1$$

$$\mathbf{Z}(k\gamma+1) = \frac{1}{T_0} \int_{t_{k\gamma}}^{t_{(k+1)\gamma}} \mathbf{X}^*(t) y_d(t) dt \quad (9)$$

where $T_0 = t_{k+1} - t_k$ is the length of the integration interval, μ is a constant that regulates convergence, γ is a positive integer, and $\alpha(i)$ is a nonnegative real number. The parameter γ determines the number of iterations of $\mathbf{Z}(i)$ that occur between weight changes. The parameter $\alpha(i)$ determines how much importance is given to old information in the computation of $\mathbf{Z}(i)$. When $\gamma > 1$, a novel feature of the Recursive Suppression algorithm is that the weights are not updated every iteration, as they are in other adaptive superresolution algorithms.

The best values of these parameters are dependent on the degree of nonstationarity in the interference. If the interference has stationary statistics over γ samples, then a suitable choice of $\alpha(i)$ is expected to be

$$\alpha(i) = \frac{i \bmod \gamma}{(i \bmod \gamma) + 1} \quad (10)$$

where $i \bmod \gamma$ denotes the nonnegative remainder when i is divided by γ . This choice weights equally the information gained during each integration interval of duration T_0 . Other choices of $\alpha(i)$ are also suitable [5].

The analytic input vector can be decomposed as

$$\mathbf{X}(t) = \mathbf{X}_R(t) + j\mathbf{X}_I(t) \quad (11)$$

where each component of $\mathbf{X}_I(t)$ is the Hilbert transform of the corresponding component of $\mathbf{X}_R(t)$. Substituting (3), (5), and (11) into (6) to (9), we can express the algorithm in terms of real variables.

The use of the real part of $y_d(t)$ in place of $y_d(t)$ yields a version of the algorithm [5] requiring half the number of multiplications per iteration as (6) to (9). However, simulation results in [5] and Section IV indicate that the accuracy of the bearing estimate decreases, particularly for $\gamma \leq 6$.

Figure 2 shows the implementation of an adaptive filter that uses the Recursive Suppression algorithm. The adaptive array is assumed to have four antenna elements, but the extension to N elements is obvious. The data processor executes (6) to (9) and performs the weight processing for the adaptive superresolution system of Figure 1. The quadrature hybrid splits the down-converted output of antenna element 1 into an in-phase component, $X_{R1}(t)$, and a quadrature component, $X_{I1}(t)$. These components are combined with the real and imaginary parts of the first element of the complex weight vector to produce weighted outputs. Similar weighted outputs from other antenna elements are combined to form the real and imaginary components of the analytic output signal, $y_d(t)$. The real component is sent to a demodulator (modem) for data extraction if the adaptive algorithm is used for adaptive interference suppression. Analog-to-digital converters produce sample values of $\mathbf{X}(t)$ and $y_d(t)$ that are applied to the data processor. The processor digitally computes the integrals of (8) and (9) and executes the Recursive Suppression algorithm.

The convergence of the mean weight vector to its optimal value can be proved by the same approximate analysis given in [5]. Let $E[\]$ denote the expected value and

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = E[\mathbf{X}^*(t) \mathbf{X}^T(t)]. \quad (12)$$

It is found that a sufficient condition for convergence is

$$0 < \mu < \frac{2}{tr(\mathbf{R}_{xx})} \quad (13)$$

where $tr(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$ denotes the trace of $\mathbf{R}_{xx}$.

III. WEIGHT PROCESSOR

Let $\mathbf{S}(t, \theta)$ denote the vector of analytic signals induced in N antenna-element outputs by a single signal source with bearing θ relative to the array. Let $T_i(\theta)$ denote the arrival-time delay at element i relative to a fixed point in space. It is often convenient to choose the fixed point at element 1 so that $T_1(\theta) = 0$. Let $s(t)$ denote the analytic signal at the fixed point. For a narrowband signal, it can be shown that [6]

$$\mathbf{S}(t, \theta) = s(t) \mathbf{S}_0(\theta) \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{S}_0(\theta)$ is the direction vector given by

$$\mathbf{S}_0(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} h_1(\theta) \exp(-j2\pi f_0 T_1) \\ h_2(\theta) \exp(-j2\pi f_0 T_2) \\ \vdots \\ h_N(\theta) \exp(-j2\pi f_0 T_N) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

and the $h_i(\theta)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, are amplitudes that depend upon the element patterns and the propagation losses. If the element patterns are identical and the elements are close enough relative to the distances to the signal source that the propagation losses to all the

Figure 2. Block diagram of Recursive Suppression algorithm.

elements are nearly the same, then the $h_i(\theta)$ are all equal. If the element patterns are isotropic and their common value is included in $s(t)$, then we can set $h_i(\theta) = 1, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. For a uniformly spaced linear array with the fixed point at element 1,

$$T_i(\theta) = \frac{(i-1)d \sin \theta}{c} \quad (16)$$

where d is the distance between adjacent elements and c is the speed of light.

The array gain pattern is defined as

$$G(\theta) = |W^T S_0(\theta)|^2 \quad (17)$$

The weight processor of Figure 1 computes this function. It has been shown [7] that the eigenvectors corresponding to the smallest eigenvalue, which span a subspace S_n , are orthogonal to the direction vectors of K narrowband received signals if $K < N$ and uncorrelated noise is present in each component of $X(t)$. Therefore, if the weight vector computed by the Recursive Suppression algorithm has nearly converged to an optimal value, which is in S_n , then $G(\theta)$ is nearly zero in the directions of the K received signals. Thus, the set of angular values that correspond to local minima of the gain pattern and also fall below a preset threshold determine the set of bearing estimates.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The Recursive Suppression algorithm was simulated on a digital computer. Four antenna elements with a half wavelength inter-element spacing were used in a linear array of aperture equal to 1.5 wavelengths. This spacing minimizes the possibility of grating nulls, thus avoiding confusion in the interpretation of the

gain pattern. The parameter β was set equal to unity. The normalized gain pattern was computed for two sinusoidal signals that arrive as plane waves with the same frequency. The bearings were set at 26 and 30 degrees, respectively, relative to the normal to the linear array. Thus, the angular separation between the two signals was slightly more than one-tenth of the array beamwidth. To decorrelate the signals and to increase their bandwidths, a random phase was added to the two sinusoids at each sample. The noise in each antenna element output was simulated as additive white Gaussian noise. The received signal-to-noise ratios were set equal to 30 dB for both signals. The integrals were digitally implemented using 16 samples per integration interval. Two bearings were considered resolved if two local gain minima appeared and each minimum was within 2 degrees of the true value of one of the bearings.

Figure 3 shows typical normalized gain patterns for $\gamma = 2$ and $\alpha(i)$ given by (10) when various numbers of iterations are performed. The adaptation constant was chosen to be $\mu = 1.6/\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$ for reasons given subsequently. Fewer than 100 iterations are needed in this simulation trial to resolve the two bearings.

Table 1 shows the averaged results of ten simulation trials with values of γ from 1 to 25 in the Recursive Suppression algorithm. The choice of $\mu = 1.6/\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$ was found to be a good one in all cases. The second column in Table 1 shows the approximate number of iterations required to achieve the resolution of the two signals. The third column lists the computed bearings while the fourth column gives the average absolute error. Columns 5 and 6 give the computed bearings and the average absolute error, respectively, at 600 iterations when the process has reached a steady state.

It is observed that the value of $\gamma = 2$ allows the resolution of the two signals after the fewest iterations. However, as illustrated when

$\gamma = 10$, there is a tradeoff between the number of iterations required for convergence and the average absolute error between the true and the computed values of a bearing. A higher number of iterations

Figure 3. Gain pattern for $\gamma = 2$.

γ	Iterations for resolution	Angles of nulls (deg.)	Avg abs. error (deg.)	Angle of nulls at 600 iterations (deg.)	Avg. abs. error (deg.)
1	236	25.9	0.49	25.8	0.45
		30.1		30.2	
2	113	25.5	0.71	25.5	0.79
		30.6		30.4	
3	171	25.4	0.83	25.6	0.81
		30.5		30.4	
4	179	25.6	0.79	25.8	0.65
		30.5		30.3	
5	210	25.8	0.58	25.7	0.41
		30.4		30.3	
6	221	26.1	0.57	26.1	0.53
		30.1		30.0	
8	231	25.9	0.43	26.1	0.33
		30.2		29.9	
10	240	26.0	0.39	25.9	0.30
		30.0		30.1	
11	238	26.0	0.38	25.9	0.50
		30.0		30.1	
12	231	26.2	0.44	25.9	0.41
		29.9		30.1	
15	244	26.0	0.32	25.9	0.31
		30.0		30.1	
20	235	26.3	0.37	26.2	0.39
		29.8		29.8	
25	248	26.3	0.32	26.0	0.21
		29.8		30.0	

tends to reduce the error. This tradeoff is analogous to the tradeoff between the speed of convergence and the misadjustment in the Widrow LMS algorithm.

When the input processes are nonstationary, the Recursive Suppression algorithm with (10) will be effective as long as there is approximate stationarity for γ or more iterations of (8) and (9). Thus, the degree of nonstationarity in the signals of interest determines an upper bound on γ .

To explain the selection of μ , we define the phenomenon of *resolution stability*. The resolution of two signals is said to be stable if the two signals are resolved in a finite number of iterations and further iterations beyond the minimum number required for resolution never cause a loss of resolution. The resolution is said to be unstable if the resolution is lost for some number of iterations exceeding the minimum number required for resolution.

Table 2 illustrates the effect of varying the adaptation constant. Each row shows the averaged results of ten simulation trials.

γ	$\mu r(R_{xx})$	Iterations for resolution	Angles of nulls (deg.)	Avg abs. error (deg.)	Angle of nulls at 600 iterations (deg.)	Avg. abs. error (deg.)
2	1.0	188	25.6	0.7	26.0	0.5
			30.4		29.9	
	1.2	145	25.6	0.64	26.0	0.6
			30.6		30.3	
	1.4	120	25.7	0.47	26.1	0.97
			30.2		30.2	
1.6	113	25.5	0.71	25.5	0.79	
		30.6		30.4		
1.8	102	25.6	0.64	25.6	0.82	
		30.6		30.9		
3	1.0	305	26.0	0.49	25.9	0.26
			30.2		30.1	
	1.2	225	25.9	0.5	26.2	0.32
			30.3		29.9	
	1.4	180	25.5	0.64	25.6	0.64
			30.6		30.6	
1.6	171	25.4	0.83	25.6	0.81	
		30.5		30.4		
1.8	125	25.4	0.73	25.7	0.63	
		30.5		30.5		
10	1.0	453	26.3	0.39	26.1	0.12
			29.6		29.9	
	1.2	320	26.3	0.48	26.1	0.26
			29.8		29.9	
	1.4	278	26.2	0.34	26.0	0.29
			29.7		30.0	
1.6	240	25.9	0.39	25.9	0.30	
		30.2		30.1		
1.8	190	26.0	0.43	25.7	0.61	
		30.2		30.3		

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Table 3. Sensitivity to Adaptation Constant When SNR = 20 dB for Both Signals						
γ	$\mu \text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$	Iterations for resolution	Angles of nulls (deg.)	Avg abs. error (deg.)	Angle of nulls at 2000 iterations (deg.)	Avg. abs. error (deg.)
2	1.0	998	25.7	0.70	26.5	0.35
			28.9		29.8	
	1.2	588	25.4	1.10	24.7	0.79
			31.6		31.0	
1.4	500	25.0	1.05	26.2	0.86	
		31.1		30.5		
1.6	458	24.7	1.35	25.1	1.15	
		31.4		31.8		
3	1.0	763	24.8	0.78	26.1	0.64
			30.3		29.4	
	1.2	675	25.1	1.20	25.4	0.93
			31.1		30.6	
1.4	650	25.8	1.60	24.2	1.30	
		32.6		31.8		
1.6	508	25.3	1.80	24.4	1.20	
		30.8		30.6		
10	1.0	688	25.0	0.49	26.1	0.15
			30.6		30.0	
	1.2	513	25.6	0.53	25.8	0.20
			30.6		29.8	
1.4	374	25.3	1.10	25.9	0.65	
		31.4		30.4		
1.6	333	25.2	0.82	25.5	0.68	
		30.8		30.3		

In general, the number of iterations required for resolution decreases as μ increases, while the average absolute error at steady state usually tends to increase. However, for $\mu = 1.8/\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$, resolution instabilities were observed in at least some trials for $\gamma = 2, 3$, and 10. Resolution stability was always observed for $\mu \leq 1.6/\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$. Thus, for a rapid and stable resolution, the choice of $\mu = 1.6/\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}_{xx})$ appears to be close to the optimal one when the received signal-to-noise ratios are 30 dB.

Table 3 illustrates the effect of varying μ when both received signal-to-noise ratios are decreased to 20 dB. Each row shows the averaged results of ten simulation trials. For all values of μ , resolution instabilities were observed in at least some trials for $\gamma = 2$ and 3. Resolution stability was always observed for $\gamma = 10$ and all values of μ . Table 3 exhibits the same tradeoff as in Table 2 between speed of resolution and average absolute error at steady state, which was always reached within 2000 iterations.

The data for the covariance-based MUSIC algorithm indicates that for sinusoidal inputs, the MUSIC algorithm can resolve the

bearings in approximately 100 iterations when the signal-to-noise ratios are 30 dB and 1000 iterations when they are 20 dB [8]. Allowing for the increased bandwidth in our simulation, the Recursive Suppression algorithm with the appropriate choice of γ seems to require a comparable number or fewer iterations. However, the MUSIC iterations must be followed by a time-consuming eigenvalue analysis or its equivalent and the evaluation of a function much more complex than the array gain pattern given by (17). Thus, the computational complexity of the MUSIC algorithm is far greater than that of the Recursive Suppression algorithm, and the time required to resolve bearings may be longer.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A new adaptive superresolution algorithm, the Recursive Suppression algorithm, has been analyzed and shown to be potentially effective. This algorithm has a parameter, γ , that can be adjusted to account for the degree of nonstationarity in the signal environment. When $\gamma > 1$, the algorithm has the novel feature that the weights are only updated after γ iterations. The number of iterations required to resolve two closely spaced sinusoidal signals appears to be comparable or fewer than the number for the MUSIC superresolution algorithm. However, the proposed algorithm is much simpler to implement and may be faster in resolving bearings.

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